

Did IceCube detect Dark Matter around Blazars?

Andrea Giovanni De Marchi
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Based on 2412.07861 AGDM, Granelli, Nava, Sala
2506.06416 AGDM, Granelli, Nava, Sala

Outline

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Blazars

AGNs

Brightest objects in the Universe! Only engine that can power this: accreting supermassive black hole (SMBH)

Urry, Padovani 1995

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If jet pointed towards Earth: **blazar**

Urry, Padovani 1995

Blazar's spectral energy distribution

Montaruli for IceCube, 2023

How to model a blazar jet

Blob moving towards Earth with Lorentz factor Γ_B , filled with extremely energetic protons and electrons

+ ambient photons from accretion disk and the jet

Leptohadronic model

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Dark Matter

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- Cold
- Collisionless
- Somewhere in this mass range:

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- PTA signal: sub-GeV dark sector phase transition? [Bringmann+ 2023]

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Dark sectors:

- Standard Model singlets, only portal interactions: allow small couplings and sub-GeV mass
- PTA signal: sub-GeV dark sector phase transition? [Bringmann+ 2023]
- 511 keV line from the galactic centre: annihilating DM? [Boehm+ 2004]

The Gondolo & Silk spike

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Ideal case, we choose as benchmarks 3000x and 10^6 x enhancement

Two complementary signals

Two complementary signals

Blazar-boosted
Dark Matter

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Neutrinos from
blazars

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Many others blazar associations:

Blazars are HE neutrino sources!

But... hard to explain

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neutrino flux

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Alternative models
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What about p-DM?

Our model

We add to the SM a fermion DM and a new massive vector that couples only to quarks (2506.06416, 2507.12278 for other Lorentz structures)

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{DM}} = g_q \bar{q} \gamma_\mu q V^\mu + g_\chi \bar{\chi} \gamma_\mu \chi V^\mu + \frac{1}{2} m_V^2 V^\mu V_\mu$$

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We can compute the flux (using MadGraph+Pythia) as

$$\frac{d\Phi_\nu}{dE_\nu} = \frac{\Sigma_{\text{los}}}{m_\chi d_L^2} \int dE_p \frac{d\Gamma_p}{dE_p d\Omega} \Big|_{\text{los}} \sigma_{\text{DIS}} \left\langle \frac{dN_\nu}{dE_\nu} \right\rangle$$

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Spike model

Jet model

Particle physics model

What we get

What we get

Probed parameter space

Blazar catalogue

Catalogue of blazars and leptohadronic fits [Rodrigues+ 2023, 2307.13024]

Diffuse neutrino flux correlates to blazar skymap above 100 TeV? [Buson+ 2022]

Parameter space

Key takeaways

- For unconstrained $\sigma_{p\chi}$, more neutrinos and lower energies from $p - \chi$ than SM.

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To do:

- What about gamma rays? Does this mess up the leptohadronic fit?
Modifying astro codes
- What about other kinds of AGN?
- Understanding the diffuse neutrino background... could this mechanism explain it?
- Is the spike normalization reasonable?
- Large astro uncertainties... can we quantify them somehow?

Thank you!

Backup

Blazar-boosted Dark Matter

Why boosted Dark Matter?

Direct detection loses sensitivity to sub-GeV DM, not enough energy to leave a signal

Two strategies:

- Lower detector threshold
- Higher DM energy

DM boosted by interaction with cosmic rays [Bringmann+ 2018; Ema+ 2018]

To do better: more cosmic rays, more DM, higher energies... **Blazars!**

[Wang+ 2021]

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Spike model

Jet model

Particle physics model

Boosted DM flux

Constraints

Big caveat: spike depletion

- As DM gets boosted away by this interaction, the spike depletes
- If depletion is faster than accretion, over time the spike disappears
- Too large cross sections are inconsistent with spike

Depletion of the spike

- Many astro effects: mergers, thermalisation with stars, BH misaligned with halo...
- DM self-scattering: very problematic, softens the spike a lot [2506.12642]. Can be avoided with inelastic DM, doesn't change the neutrino signal
- Jet depletion of the spike:

$$\Sigma_{DM} = \int_{R_{min}}^R \textit{spike} dr \rho(r) \exp\{-A \langle \sigma \rangle t/r^2\}$$

Different jet model

The Gondolo & Silk spike

Dark Matter around SMBH in the center of galaxies accumulates into spikes

As SMBH grows, it contracts orbit around it, turns $r^{-\gamma}$ into $r^{-(9-2\gamma)/(4-\gamma)}$

[Gondolo, Silk 1999]

For $\Sigma_{\text{los}} = \int_{r_{\text{min}}}^{r_{\text{max}}} dr \rho(r)$, up to 8-9 orders of magnitude more than NFW ($\Sigma_{\text{los}}^{\text{NFW}} \approx 10^{23} \text{ GeV cm}^{-2}$)

Ullio, Zhao, Kamionkowski 2001

UV completion bounds

Dror, Lasenby, Pospelov 2017

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Available parameter space (0.5 GeV)

Available parameter space (10 GeV)

Available parameter space (axial)

Available parameter space (scalar)

Available parameter space (pseudo)

Monochromatic

A bit of history

In 1950s, discovery of radio-sources associated to optical star-like sources, with unusual emission lines and color.

Classified as **Quasi-stellar radio sources (Quasars)**

In 1963 first spectrum of 3C273 (Schmidt): Hydrogen lines with $z = 0.158$, cosmological distance!

Not stars, brighter than entire galaxies!

$$L \sim 10^{13} L_{\odot}$$

Steidel, NASA/ESA, 1996

